

Poem by Bharati Nayak

I Am Still A Pebble Very Ordinary

I am an ordinary pebble
Thrown by the stream side
Before that I went through
Many cycles of run downs
My edges smoothed
My body shined
But, I am still an ordinary pebble
Once you picked up
Perhaps looked at me with curiosity
and put me in your pocket absentmindedly
And I was put into a washing machine
Along with your dress
I am moving round and round
And you forgot to switch off
The machine still runs
Me in endless circles.

@Bharati Nayak
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Bio

Bharati Nayak, is an internationally recognized bilingual poet, critique and translator from Bhubaneswar, India. Her poems have been published in about hundred books and journals. . She has published three poetry books- 1-Padma Paada (Odia language) 2-Words Are Such Perfect Traitors 3-A Day for Myself. She has co-authored three books namely Radical Rhythm ,vol-1,Vol-2 and Vol-3 and worked as the Editor for Radical Rhythm Vol-3.

A regular writer at popular website www.poemhunter.com ,she is placed among top 500 world poets and has been offered a title 'Poetic Basil' .

She has been conferred with Sahitya Lahari award by International Cosmos Society, India in 2018 and Star Ambassador of World Poetry And Art Philosophique Poetica International Award in Literature in 2019.